

NPOWER
BALANCING N & P FLOWS

D.1.2

MATs Methodology

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The NPower Project

NPower aims to reduce nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) emissions and rebalance nutrient flows across key sectors in Europe. By advancing nutrient recovery technologies, best management practices (BMPs), and governance measures, the project will contribute to more efficient and circular nutrient use, minimising environmental impact while supporting agricultural and industrial sustainability.

Running for four years from January 2025, NPower will:

- Develop an innovative N/P budgeting software model to analyse and optimise nutrient flows across five key emitting sectors.
- Demonstrate six nutrient recovery technologies to produce sustainable fertilisers.
- Promote 20 best management practices to improve nutrient efficiency and reduce emissions.
- Design and implement governance measures to support effective nutrient management policies at local, regional, and EU levels.
- Facilitate knowledge transfer across four Regional Clusters (RCs) in Spain, Belgium, Finland, and Ireland to ensure EU-wide applicability.

Spain will serve as the main demonstration site, implementing recovery technologies, while the other RCs will assess their applicability and potential replication in their respective contexts.

Led by a consortium of 25 partners from across Europe, NPower integrates expertise from research, industry, and policy, covering the entire N/P value chain. This collaboration will provide practical, scalable solutions to optimise nutrient cycles and support the EU's sustainability goals.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
BMP	Best Management Practice
CAP	Common Agriculture Policy
CB	Capacity Building
CBSW	Circular Bioeconomy cluster South West (Ireland)
DoA	Description of Action
EASW	European Awareness Scenario Workshops
EU	European Union
FMRM	Federation of Municipalities of Region of Murcia
F2F	Face-to-face
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	GreenHouse Gases
IAP2	International Association for Public Participation
KOM	Kick-Off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
MAT	MultiActor Transition Group
MTU	Munster Technical University
N	Nitrogen
NCCP	National Coordinating Centre for Public Engagement
OTPC	Office for Transparency and Citizen Participation
P	Phosphorus
PA	Practice Abstract

Acronym	Description
RC	Regional Cluster
So-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
ToC	Theory of Change
WP	Work Package

1. Executive summary

This document constitutes the deliverable D1.2 MATs Methodology and describes the activities to be developed in Npower project by the Multi-actor transition groups (MATs). The activity is framed within NPower WP1 *Establishment of multi-actor transition groups within EU Regional Clusters*, that aims at establishing 20 Multiactor Transition Groups (MATs) belonging to 4 Regional Clusters (RCs): RC1 in Murcia (Spain), RC2 in Belgium, RC3 in Finland and RC4 in Ireland. Specifically, it is outlined in Task 1.1, to design the conceptual framework for stakeholder engagement, which is defined as the [strategic process for interacting](#) with stakeholders (practitioners, researchers and policy makers) to understand shared interests, preferences, and potential for collaboration.

The MATs Methodology relies on IAP2 Core Values for Public Participation aligned with the Ethical principles further detailed in Deliverable 8.2 of NPower project. It contains activities encompassing different levels of participation (informative level, consultive level and collaborative level), that have been selected following IAP2's Spectrum of Public Participation to define the stakeholders' role in any engagement process. The Methodology is also underpinned by conceptual multi-actor models, explained in the [Theoretical Framework](#).

The first step to design the MATs methodology has been an [Ecosystem mapping](#), where information on existing resources for public participation, both in terms of relevant stakeholders and infrastructures, in the different Regional Clusters (Murcia, Belgium, Finland and Ireland) has been gathered.

Subsequently, in section [Methods and tools](#), the different levels of public engagement to be used in the NPower project (informative level, consultive level and collaborative level) were analysed and compared to the activities foreseen in the NPower description of Action. In this way, the MATs methodology aims to facilitate decision making on those tools or methods that are most suitable for the MATs activities according to the goals of the specific action, its complexity and sensitivity. The methodologies to be applied, including quantitative and qualitative procedures to collect the information from the MATs activities, and templates to facilitate their implementation and ensure the reproducibility along the different RCs, are described in detail in the [Annex](#).

In section [Action Plan](#), an action-oriented timeline has been elaborated based on the ecosystem analysis and the diagnosis, in which concrete activities are defined together with the required resources and responsibilities. The action plan is developed in a collaborative way, revised and adjusted along the project lifecycle.

Finally, the section [Conclusion](#) collects the lessons learnt during the MATs activities and how these can be applied to other activities.

D1.2 MATs methodology

As the MATs methodology is a living document that will be launched on M9 (September 2025) and updated during the whole project duration, it is recommended to apply the lessons learnt during the activities (for instance, the engagement of stakeholders achieved during the MATs KOM) in forthcoming tasks such as those in WP4 (Identification and selection of relevant BMPs at regional and EU level, and demonstration of N/P balancing BMPs), WP5 (Development and showcasing of innovative governance measures, and capacity building for effective implementation) and WP7 (EU potential for replicating circularity) identifying and analysing opportunities to ensure the replicability of project results.

2. Introduction

According to NPower project Description of the Action (DoA), *D1.2 MATs Methodology* in NPower is a report on the description of the methodology developed in Task 1.1 to be followed by the multi-actor transition groups (MATs). D1.2 is framed within Work Package (WP) 1, that aims at establishing 20 Multiactor Transition Groups (MATs) belonging to 4 Regional Clusters (RCs): RC1 in Murcia (Spain), RC2 in Belgium, RC3 in Finland and RC4 in Ireland. A minimum of 12 MATs will be established, as Key Performance Indicator (KPI) for this task.

The aim of D1.2 is to design the conceptual framework for stakeholder engagement, which is defined as the strategic process for interacting with stakeholders to understand shared interests, preferences, and potential for collaboration, involving gathering input to inform decision-making in a way that benefits all parties and enhances the sustainability of outcomes (Franklin, 2020). Engagement is by definition a two-way process, involving interaction and listening, with the goal of generating mutual benefit (National Coordinating Centre for Public Engagement (NCCPE), 2014).

NPower engagement strategy relies on IAP2 Core Values for Public Participation (IAP2, 2022), ensuring that the participation of stakeholders takes into account interests and concerns of potentially affected stakeholders, aligned with the Ethical principles that were further detailed in Deliverable 8.2 of NPower project (launched in M6, June 2025). In addition, the IAP2's Spectrum of Public Participation (Susskind and Carson, 2008) will be used as basis to select of the level of participation that defines the stakeholders' role in any engagement process. The 5 IAP2 levels have been adapted in NPOWER to a three-level approach (inform, consult, collaborate) due to operative reasons, in order to classify stakeholders and define tailored tools and methods in each activity, according to its nature and complexity.

In WP1, the first task to be accomplished will be the consolidation of actors from the 5 key N/P emitting sectors, to set up the RCs. Each RC will be led by a local research/technology institute or university participating in NPower consortium, supported by policy experts/public administrations and institutions in direct contact with practitioners from the key emitting sectors (Figure 1) but they will be enlarged to reach minimum 10 stakeholders per RC (2 in each MAT).

Figure 1. Distribution of MATs in the Regional Clusters and Regional Clusters leaders

These stakeholders will be different actors of the landscape of N/P emissions, recruited to represent the different sectors of the Quintuple Helix of Innovation (Carayannis et al., 2012) bringing together public administration, private industry, research sector, and civil society in the creation and transformation of knowledge within the framework of the environment (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Quintuple helix of stakeholders

These RCs will participate in the remaining WPs, providing input to guarantee the replicability of NPower solutions in the four regions covered by NPower RCs.

Subsequently, each RC will launch 5 multi-actor transition groups (MATs), and the RC leaders will direct a series of 5 workshops in which each MAT will define their N/P-containing inputs and outputs (to air, soil, and water).

In addition to the workshops mentioned in WP1, the MATs that will be leveraged to involve key stakeholders throughout NPower project activities.

- In WP2, the MATs in the RC1 (Murcia) will be involved in the validation of the N/P budget, to be elaborated by UGENT.
- In WP3, the RCs will evaluate the replicability of N/P recovery technologies demonstrated in RC1
- In WP4, the RCs will facilitate the coordination, dialogue, and collaboration among regional N/P stakeholders, strengthening regional cohesion among these stakeholders. Moreover, they will contribute to identify and share regional BMPs and validate those from other RCs
- In WP5, the RCs will identify and share their governance measures, and participate in the co-creation of innovative ones, and the proposition of policies and regulations aiming to limit N/P emissions and re-balance N/P flows. They will also contribute to the evaluation of political actions (at regional, municipal, and national scale) and collaborate in the design of multi-actor transition pathways for a sustainable integrated N/P management
- In WP6, the RCs will steer the contribution of MATs to the impact analysis, specifically by facilitating their input on the adoption of NPower solutions within society and assessing social acceptance through online questionnaires and [focus groups workshops](#). In addition, RCs will provide guidance and support in generating insights for evaluating the readiness to change towards the adoption of new technologies or processes.
- In WP7, the RCs will collaborate promoting synergies and sectorial awareness to support circular business models and value chains based on NPower recovery technologies and recovered fertilizers and contribute to the communication and dissemination of relevant information (including project results such as Practice Abstracts - PAs, guidelines and policy recommendations), encouraging behavioural change and public acceptance within and outside the RCs.

2.1. Theoretical framework

NPower MATs methodology is based on conceptual multi-actor models (bio-district models, causal, affected and managing actors' model, the complexity theory) and the fundamentals of the Theory of Change approach.

Conceptual multiactor models

Biodistrict model

Biodistricts, also known as organic districts or eco-regions, are territorial systems that draw from concepts in agroecology, socio-economic transformation, and the bioeconomy, to promote sustainable development integrating agroecological transformation, biodiversity protection, inclusive governance with local-based approaches and rural revitalization (FAO, 2017). Biodistricts or ecoregions are defined as *“non-administrative, but functional, geographical area, in which an alliance is established between farmers, citizens, tour operators, associations and public administrations, for the sustainable management of resources”* (Basile, 2014). Biodistricts encompass 3 main dimensions: the environmental dimension, tackling the protection of biodiversity and the use of agroecological principles; the social dimension, based on the development of a sustainable and inclusive territory centred on the farmers to promote social aggregation and cultural exchange; and the economic dimension, focused on the obtention of economic benefits through innovative economic activities that increase the territorial value and provide access to markets (Dias et al., 2021).

In NPower, the concept of Biodistricts guides the conceptualisation of the 5 Regional Clusters, in which stakeholders representing different sectors (public administrations, researchers and academia, practitioners and associations) generate alliances to overcome environmental issues and foster sustainable development.

Causal, affected and managing actors' model

The causal, affected and managing actors' model is a theoretical framework that provides a deeper understanding on how actions and processes within organisations and groups drive changes, analysing influences between actors (Burke and Litwin, 1992; Vlachos et al., 2017). Causal actors are the individuals or groups whose actions generate changes or outcomes; affected actors are those who experience the outcomes of the actions taken by the causal actors; and managing actors are those that can oversee or regulate the interactions between causal and affected actors. These groups are not mutually exclusive, as causal actors can themselves suffer the outcomes of their actions, and managing actors may take actions with negative outcomes for affected actors (Oude Lansink et al., 2018).

In NPower, the causal, affected and managing actors' model will be used to identify mutual relationships and roles among the stakeholders involved in the different Regional Clusters established, that can be relevant to organise participatory actions and to design policy recommendations.

Complexity theory

The complexity theory analyses how systems composed of many interacting parts give rise to emergent, unpredictable features that cannot be understood by analysing components in isolation, assuming that “the whole is qualitatively different from the sum of its parts” (Byrne and Callaghan, 2022). Complexity theory was initially applied to ecological sciences, but it can also be used in social sciences to understand and assess governance processes. It emphasizes the principles: i) emergence, indicating those emergent patterns and properties that arise from interactions between the components of the system, that cannot be reduced to individual parts); ii) non-linearity (indicating that small changes may have disproportionate cascade effects); iii) adaptation, since boundaries between complex systems and their environments blur due to exchange processes; and iv) self-organization, as complex system evolve and adapt to their environments, due to the adaptation mentioned before.

In NPower, principles of complexity theory will be applied to the MAT methodology to underpin the analysis of governance models and policy making in the management of natural resources (soil, water, air, nutrients) that may lead to issues like N and P pollution, where multilevel processes (local, regional, interregional...) take place.

Theory of Change

A Theory of Change (ToC) is defined as a narrative “*describing the whole chain of influences (from outputs to impacts) of a project or program up to its intended contribution to improve the lives of people in poverty, which is the ultimate aim of all our interventions*”.(Goodier et al., 2018). ToC represents a structured framework widely used to map out and clarify the causal pathways of a change that is expected to happen, as certain intervention takes place through a sequence of intermediate steps, making the assumptions between these steps explicit.(Koleros, et al., 2024) and have been ubiquitously used for designing interventions, understanding and agreeing on interventions with stakeholders, designing monitoring systems for impact evaluation, evaluating proposed interventions and reporting performance of interventions (Mayne, 2015)

In NPower, ToC will be used in participatory activities (focus groups, impact planning workshops) aiming to understand the effects of policies and management practices addressing current challenges in the reduction of N and P pollution in ecosystems.

3. Ecosystem mapping

Engaging stakeholders requires mapping the different interest groups related to the project, in the context of the 4 RCs. As stated in the theoretical framework, the circularisation of N/P flows may be determined by the diversity of regional contexts (including the range of actors, governance and legislative mechanisms, resources and discourses), it is necessary to attempt to classify stakeholders to better understand those that may support, oppose or be neutral about the projects results (Dieken et al., 2021).

In NPower, stakeholders have been assessed using the Stakeholders Classification Matrix, that defines the stakeholder's "stake" in a certain project based on the two variables of power and interest (Mainardes et al., 2012) to group and prioritise stakeholders considering their role or potential impact (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Stakeholder mapping and types of engagement

For each of the stakeholder groups, it is crucial to also identify their motivations, needs and interests. It is important to note however that the outcomes of WP1 (specifically the workshops to be performed with the MATs) will play a key role in further identifying these motivations and needs and in helping partners design tailored activities along the project lifecycle.

The mapping and assessment of the stakeholders have been performed through collaborative sessions in the Kick Off Meeting of each RC, where motivations and needs based on previous experiences were also discussed to set up the MATs. Some of these motivations and needs are included in in Table 1.

Table 1. Stakeholders' needs and motivations

Stakeholder group		Motivations	Needs
	Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research opportunities Availability of data Replication and scale up of technologies in other regions 	Knowledge transfer
	Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overload of regulations at different levels (EU, national...) Lack of integration of regulations Lack of funding programmes (i.e. CAP agroecological supporting programme) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased acceptance of policies and strategies Evidence based policies and strategies
	Practitioners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased prize of synthetic fertilisers Restrictions of Nitrates directive and emissions (livestock, industry) Lack of incentives and high costs of production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Affordable fertilisers and water resources Market access Training and examples of validated technologies and best practices Business models
	Civil society representatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better quality of life (reduced pollution, increased participation in governance models, training and work opportunities) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clean environment Participative governance models Environmentally friendly products with traceable/trusted labels

3.1. Stakeholder database

Once the stakeholders were detected in the corresponding RC KoM, the leaders of each RC were responsible for translating the information into a stakeholder database in form of a spreadsheet, including the information required on organisations to be contacted in the different engagement levels

The database is hosted in NPower internal repository and will be available for all partners (considering ethical issues such as the protection of personal data) to consult the registered stakeholders. A copy of the database including only the

3.2. Mapping engagement infrastructure

This step entails gathering information on existing resources for the public participation in the context of the project, that is, for each of the different RCs foreseen in NPower project, both in terms of relevant infrastructure and strategies, to establish synergies and avoid overlap.

Participation infrastructures entail:

- Virtual infrastructures including online platforms and tools, application software, and collaborative channels designed to engage stakeholders at various levels (Inform, Consult, Collaborate). They do not include public services or information platforms that do not facilitate active participation in decision-making processes.
- Face-to-face (F2F) infrastructures refer to governance infrastructures and physical spaces dedicated to the citizen engagement based in the district, city, regional or pilot level. Participatory groups and structures aimed at increasing the citizens' influence on decision-making on NPower topics are analysed.

The following infrastructures have been detected through desk research and a survey performed among NPower beneficiaries members of the RCs (M4-M6).

3.2.1. RC1 Murcia

Region of Murcia participation platform: it is a virtual infrastructure (<https://participa.carm.es/>, Figure 5) aimed at the Region's citizens as well as citizen organisations having the region as their main area of activity. This technological platform is managed by CARM and specifically, by the Office for Transparency and Citizen Participation (OTPC). It allows the diffusion, and the management of the citizen participation tools, promoting channels to interact with regional administrations in designing and evaluating public policies. The website also includes links to different territorial scopes of participation, such as the municipalities, communities of citizens from Murcia in other Spanish regions and abroad, participation at the national and the EU level, as well as resources and information for associations. Other contents provide information on activities to promote citizen participation, such as workshops or funding.

Currently, the platform foresees 5 types of participative processes: citizen contributions, public consultations, participative deliberation processes, citizen participation forums and citizen initiatives: Currently, there are no open participatory processes.

Figure 5. Citizen participatory platform (Region of Murcia)

Sectoral Councils: Different types of collegiate bodies operate in the Region of Murcia, among which those related to the topics of NPower are the Regional Agricultural Advisory Council, the Regional Advisory Council of Agriculture Professional Organisations and the Regional Environmental Advisory Council, which count with the representation of policy makers and practitioners in the field of agriculture. These bodies meet the requirement of the government (President, Vice-president, or Regional Councillors). The sectoral councils will be informed about NPower results, and members will be invited to take part in the MATs.

3.2.2. RC2 Belgium

Nutricycle Vlaanderen: it is a virtual engagement platform managed by UGENT in Flanders (<https://nutricycle.vlaanderen>, in Dutch language) with the mission of realising the transition to circular economy in nutrients flows. The platform is aimed at the agricultural sector, the business community, centres of excellence, civil society organisation and government, acting as point of contact among these stakeholders, connecting them and easing knowledge transfer. Nutricycle Vlaanderen gathers information on different innovations and initiatives that exist in Flanders in the field of recuperation and recycling of mineral nutrients to promote the exchange of information, promotes dissemination and communication translating research results into informative brochures, newsletters and organising [targeted events](#) such as webinars and workshops. In

addition, it allows surveying stakeholders on their needs and offers a framework in the form of an Action Plan “Transition nutrient removal to nutrient recovery” in which co-ownership is stimulated.

3.2.3. RC3 Finland

ProAgria: ProAgria is a member-owner organisation (<https://www.proagria.fi>) for farms and rural businesses that provides on farm advisory and development services for members and customers, through their network of 8 regional centres and the Association and the Association of ProAgria Centres. The organisation develops projects for rural development and provides advisory services on different issues (among them business and financial management, livestock production, plant production and climate solutions) supported by an integrated knowledge management system and Advisor Academy for in-service training. The infrastructure will allow informing farmers on the advances and activities of the project through the section Projects of their website.

3.2.4. RC4 Ireland

Circular Bioeconomy Cluster SouthWest (CBSW): Is a private regional cluster (<https://cbcsw.ie/>) initiated in 2021 by Munster Technological University (MTU), CircBio Research Group and Enterprise Ireland focused on circular bioeconomy. They address 3 main areas: agriculture, developing projects and products to reduce GHG emissions and waste; marine, developing biobased products from marine materials and byproducts; and waste to value, creating products and materials from by-products and waste. They offer services to members related to the identification of collaborative projects, market connections and knowledge transfer activities, training and capacity building programmes, attracting funding and marketing through social media. In NPower, this infrastructure will be useful as a platform for disseminating activities and events, due to the participation of MTU as member of the cluster.

Irish Nutrient Sustainability Platform (<https://www.nutrientsustainability.ie/>) is a platform funded with the aim of promoting sustainable nutrient management on the island of Ireland in the context of the [United Nations Sustainable Development Goals Agenda](#). The platform works as a non-for profit, funded by Department of Communications, Climate Action and Environment and administered by the Environmental Protection Agency. The platform brings together different stakeholders such as universities, industry representatives and public environmental administrations, offering members support for the creation of business opportunities, spaces to discuss challenges and innovations with regulators, networking and knowledge exchange, corporate visibility and access to funding opportunities, through different activities such as workshops, or showcase events. In NPower, the network will serve to engage stakeholders in the MATs, offering the opportunity of organising joint events and disseminate results

4. Stakeholder Engagement & Communication

Figure 6. NPower website with link to the Expression of Interest to join the different Regional Clusters

The RC leaders are responsible for coordinating stakeholder engagement and onboarding efforts with their RC partners. LOOP and KVC will provide with methods, tools and materials to support this engagement, such as:

- Expression of interest from stakeholders (Figure 6), as a form including information on NPower project published in the website, to collect contact information on potential actors interested in taking part in the RCs. The Expression of interest has been published in local language and linked to a QR code appearing in materials (flyers, posters) to be shown and distributed during face-to-face in events. Each RC leader will receive the responses to the form and translate the information to the stakeholder database.

[Expression of interest- RC1 Murcia](#)

[Expression of Interest- RC 2 Belgium](#)

Expression of Interest- RC3 Finland

Expression of Interest- RC4 Ireland

- MATs one-pager: is a printable material designed by LOOP, that can be tailored to prospective stakeholders, with customisable features depending on the region and target MAT group that can be highlighted to promote participation in NPower RCs. These features include the benefits and motivations enumerated in Table 1, and others based on the event format and additional features (participation of key lecturers and guest speakers, cross-fertilisation with other events and initiatives, and side activities like field visits and open days to research facilities)

Figure 7. NPower one pager English version

5. Methods and tools

According to the three levels of public engagement defined in [Introduction](#), tailored tools or methods will be selected for the MATs activities. KVC, LOOP and STRANE will support the RCs in engaging the stakeholders, taking into consideration information provided by partners and the respective regional stakeholders collected through surveys, questionnaires, and literature review in WP1.

Specifically, LOOP and STRANE will support Informative participation through the activities to be performed in WP7 (newsletters, website, etc). For consultative and collaborative participation, KVC will oversee analysing and identifying the type of method or tool that best suits in each case. The methods and tools listed in Table 2, have been summarised in Annex.

Table 2 Summary of methods according to the engagement level

Informative participation	Consultative participation	Collaborative participation
Dissemination and communication materials (Newsletters, Fact Sheets, Web sites, social media, Policy briefs) Webinars and capacity building activities Practice Abstracts	Surveys and questionnaires Focus groups Workshops	Impact mapping World Café Scenario planning Role Playing

An Internal Document (RCs Toolkit) prepared by KVC, together with MTU, LOOP and STRANE, providing more detail to the RC leaders to help organise and guide the public engagement activities.

5.1. Informative participation

Represents the most basic level in public participation, in which information only flows one-way providing stakeholders the necessary knowledge and skills to fully understand the project's actions and reach their own conclusions. Some authors consider that the inform level should cover the entire spectrum, since effective engagement requires effective information (Chappell, 2016; Susskind and Carson, 2008). This level is appropriate in situations where there is no opportunity for public influence and simply informing them is appropriate. This way, although informing does not imply soliciting input or feedback, or participation per se, it increases the understanding of issues, stakeholders' and communities' ability to address them, and compliance with regulation.

5.2. Consultative participation

Consults represent the minimum opportunity for the public to give their input on analysis, alternatives, or decisions, being appropriate whenever specific input is sought from experts or citizens for the decision-making, but early engagement is not possible throughout the process. In this case, the ultimate responsibility for decisions remains with the government or the organisations doing the consulting. There is wide range of ways to perform consultations, some of which include processes that require little to no dialogue (surveys in a newsletter or digital platforms) while others entail debate (public meetings, focus groups).

5.3. Collaborate level

At the Collaborate level, stakeholders are actively engaged in shaping activities and outputs, in an interactive two-way process. Hence, the collaborate level includes an explicit attempt to find consensus solutions, although the administration or project management board remains the ultimate decision-maker. This level entails creating trust and ensuring genuine engagement, which can be costly and time-consuming. The Collaborate level is particularly useful for controversial issues and complex problems because it entails a high level of participation.

6. Action Plan

The following section presents a set of preliminary activities suitable for each level of participation proposed. Nevertheless, it must be taken into consideration that the action plan is dynamic, and it will be updated in a collaborative manner by all involved partners. These methods are intended as guidance, and each partner can determine the most appropriate approach within their specific context.

6.1. Inform Level

The Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DEC) Plan (D7.2) was elaborated (M6, June 2025) and will be updated in M22 (D7.3, October 2026) and M36 (D7.4, December 2027), led by LOOP with the support of STRANE and WE. It will provide an in-depth plan for the informative level of participation (see Figure 8).

where they will learn about NPower's kit of governance measures to limit and re-balance N/P emissions. In these workshops, participants will also reflect on supporting mechanisms to be promoted between different policy levels to effectively implement these measures. These will be held on-site and made available as webinars, as well as be included in training platforms and offered to the Spanish Federation of Municipalities to increase reach.

- Workshop for EU Policy Recommendations: To support policy adaptation at EU level and promote the implementation of NPower's innovative governance solutions, a dedicated workshop will be organised in Brussels by FMRM, as part of Task 6.3, to present three policy recommendations developed in the project, based on the most relevant outcomes from WP2-WP6. The environmental, economic, and social impacts of the project's recovery technologies, solutions, and BMPs will be evaluated through Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Techno-Economic Analysis (TEA), and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) and the results will be compiled in policy recommendations for EU policymakers to be presented in an on-site event in Brussels. This workshop will serve as an opportunity to raise awareness and engage directly with policymakers and institutional stakeholders. Specifically, it will target representatives of (i) European institutions, (ii) covenant of mayors, and (iii) network of local entities involved in implementing the 2030 Agenda.
- CB workshops for practitioners (WP7): As part of NPower's capacity building efforts, dedicated workshops will be organised within Task 7.1 (communication activities) to support EU practitioners in understanding and applying solutions, fostering their adoption and replication across Europe. These capacity building workshops will serve to present and discuss the BMPs deemed easier to adopt, out of 20 BMPs (from 4 clusters and 5 sectors) demonstrated through desk research and sectorial stakeholder collaboration in T4.2. Workshops will be accompanied by Practice Abstracts.

Practice Abstracts

The consortium will produce 40 Practice Abstracts (PAs) in three batches (10, 10, and 20) to present NPower's solutions to regional and European audiences, as outline in the DEC Plan. Available in English, Spanish, and other relevant languages, the PAs will explain selected Best Management Practices (BMPs), their benefits, and practical steps for implementation, aiming to support adoption and replication. They will include a brief project overview, description of the practice, key findings, lessons learned and estimated costs and benefits. Written in clear, non-technical language, the PAs will be targeted at practitioners, policymakers, and other stakeholders, and will also feed into WP5 governance measures and Task 2.2 N/P budgeting for the Region of Murcia.

6.2. Consult level

At the consult level, key stakeholders from the main sectors responsible for N/P emissions will be engaged through the NPower’s Regional Clusters. Their participation will primarily involve providing input, feedback, and sector-specific insights to inform other work packages (see Figure 9), especially on how to guarantee the replicability of NPower’s solutions in other contexts. Their involvement will be through qualitative and quantitative methods such as surveys, questionnaires, focus groups, and workshops, allowing to collect relevant information and identify sectoral challenges and opportunities.

Figure 9. Action Plan at consultation level

Online consultation for RCs baseline (WP1)

A baseline consultation was conducted via an online questionnaire (guided by a Toolkit developed before the Kick-off-Meeting) to set up the RCs and better understand each region’s context. Regional Cluster leaders were tasked with carrying out a territorial mapping exercise to establish this baseline, covering aspects such as identifying the industrial landscape, understanding agricultural activities, assessing energy sources, and evaluating waste management systems.

Data collection for N/P budget (WP2)

NPower will develop and implement an N/P budgeting software model for Murcia, Spain, considering inputs and outputs from the 5 key emitting sectors, as well as their environmental, economic and behavioural impacts. Data will be collected through direct interaction with stakeholders, covering local and regional (Murcia) level emissions. With special support of practitioner representatives, MATs’ input will be gathered through interviews and online surveys. This will be coordinated by UGENT, which will provide guidance on the specific information required. All data collection activities will follow the project’s ethical and gender standards.

Environmental, technoeconomic and social Impact assessments (WP6)

WP6, coordinated by KVC, will assess the environmental, economic, and social impacts of NPower solutions. Each partner overlooks one specific section under KVC’s coordination: ZHAW will lead the performance of environmental and economic analysis through Life-Cycle Assessments (LCA) of practices and technologies, while KVC will lead the impact assessment of NPower’s solutions on society (so-LCA) (e.g., improvement of social conditions, contribution to social development, etc.).

The So-LCA will target external stakeholders participating in the Regional Clusters, while the environmental and technoeconomic assessments will primarily involve RCs (internal stakeholders). Data will be collected using questionnaires and surveys, disseminated via platforms such as JotForm, SurveyMonkey, or the EU Survey platform, selected according to accessibility and audience preferences.

6.3. Collaborate level

At the Collaborate level, stakeholders are actively engaged in shaping NPower’s activities and outputs (Figure 10). This process began with the Kick-off Meetings of the Regional Clusters, where project partners jointly identified relevant stakeholders and carried out a mapping exercise to find key actors within the N/P emissions landscape.

Figure 10. Action Plan at collaborate level

Sectoral Workshops: from September to November 2025, each RC will conduct five workshops (one per sector) bringing together both project partners and recruited external stakeholders. These sessions will be used to welcome stakeholders to the RCs and explore the specific needs and expectations of each sector, as well as to identify the nitrogen and phosphorus inputs and outputs relevant to their activities, feeding the NP budget to be elaborated by UGENT in WP2. The workshops will follow the structure and resources provided in the toolkit:

- Workshop MAT1. Agriculture

- Workshop MAT2. Other primary sectors
- Workshop MAT3. Water and waste management
- Workshop MAT4. Energy and transport
- Workshop MAT5. Other industrial sectors

Sectoral Workshops for BMPs identification: Under T4.1, each RC will organise one workshop per MAT (total 5 workshops), where participants will review existing BMPs, share their own N/P-limiting or circular practices, and explore possible unexploited BMPs through suitable methods such as [World Café](#) or [focus groups](#).

RC Workshop for BMP exchange: After BMP identification, RCs will organise one workshop gathering all MATs to discuss BMPs identified in other RCs. KVC will provide support in the workshops, creating detailed guidelines for partners. Techniques like [Scenario Planning](#), or [Focus Groups](#), will help participants envision how BMPs from other regions could work in their own context, considering constraints and opportunities.

Workshops to create multi-actor transition pathways: In T5.1, NPower will study regional political actions and governance measures, and through workshops with MATs will identify the missing aspects preventing their effective adoption. MATs will analyse project results and participate in creating multi-actor transition pathways for sustainable integrate N/P management in the future, including steps for implementation, barriers and risks. To support this process, the workshops may apply [Impact Mapping](#), [Role Playing](#) and [Scenario Planning](#) as techniques.

7. Conclusion

As an initial methodology document, the content of D1.2 will be revised and updated over the course of NPower project to ensure its maximum effectiveness guiding the partners in the organisation of participatory activities involving MATs. Additional materials may be also prepared, for internal use, providing more detailed guidance on the methodologies described- In December 2026 the document will be internally updated and feedback from RC leaders and external advisors in the mid-term review incorporated.

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9. Annex: Methods for public engagement

9.1. Surveys, questionnaires and interviews

Duration

Variable. It depends on the questions (number and type). We should inform the respondents on the estimated time required.

Targeted participants

Usually individual

Resources

- For interviews:
 - A skilled facilitator to implement the interview (familiar with topics and speaker of the interviewee' language)
 - Guide for the interview, including introduction, questions and closing (with thank-you message)
 - For online interview, Telephone or videocall software (teams, Google Meet, Webex)
 - If carried face-to-face, a room where we can perform the interview without interruptions and preserving privacy.
 - Audio recorder o videorecorder to register the interview and to ease the subsequent transcription of results. In online interviews, teleconference tools offer this possibility.
- For questionnaires:
 - Guide for the questionnaire (questions) including introduction on the purpose of the questionnaire, information on who will hold and manage the data, and thanks message at the end)
 - If the survey is performed online, some examples of questionnaire or survey platforms that can be used are Microsoft forms (preferred option due to GDPR aspects), Jotform (<https://www.jotform.com>), or SurveyMonkey (<https://www.surveymonkey.com/>). The EU Platform EU Survey

(<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/>) may also constitute a useful tool for consultations.

Procedure

- Prepare carefully the guide with the questions.
- For interviews, different channels can be used: telephone, presential meeting or videoconferences. We should have a speech to guide the interview, including the consent for recording that will ease the transcription and analysis of results.
- Test the interview or survey internally with people not related to the topic or project, to ensure that the questions are understood, and the time for answering is not excessive (more than 1 hour of interview is considered too long). Providing this information at the beginning of the survey or even in the recruiting email will help the respondent to estimate a time and will avoid dropouts before completing
- Analysis of results. It is convenient to give feedback to the respondents, so that they perceive that their effort and time is taken into consideration.

9.2. Focus Groups

Focus groups are a technique used to explore public issues/attitudes/preferences/trends on a specific topic. They encourage discussion and are good for deepening the understanding of how people think and feel about issues. A main interest group can be targeted. More precisely, stakeholders can be carefully selected to represent a designated part of the population, or to represent different positions.

Focus groups are used when it is important to gather community views, but there is not enough time to do one-on-one interviews. A focus group can deliver the same results as a survey in less time and for less cost. They are very useful where there are a number of complex issues that need specific attention to resolve them. Focus groups are not just the sum of individual interviews. Thus, the moderator must always initiate and maintain a dynamic interaction between the participants. However, the moderator's interaction in a focus group should be relatively limited and carefully managed to avoid influencing, suggesting, or biasing the discussion. The goal is to help the conversation flow smoothly and prevent it from getting stuck on certain points, rather than directing or dominating the exchange.

Conducting a number of focus groups in different locations and with different participants may provide enough data to cross reference and verify a result.

Duration

2-4 hours.

Targeted participants

7 to 10 people (when face-to-face); 4-5 (when online)

Resources

- A meeting room to seat 7 to 10 people comfortably at tables in a u-shape setting. If we plan to make breakout sessions, we will need several rooms.
- Laptop, data projector, screen
- Hard copies and PowerPoint reference material on the topic
- A skilled facilitator to implement the focus group: the facilitator should be well informed of the evaluation's topics and goals, be familiar with all the techniques relating to group interaction and speak the language of the participants (if breakout sessions are performed, we will need a facilitator for each group)
- A note taker familiar with transcription of focus groups and digital tools used in the workshop (if breakout sessions are performed, we will need a notetaker for each group)
- Well prepared discussion guide to moderate and structure the focus group.
- Audio recorder or videorecorder may be needed to register the focus group and the subsequent transcription of results. In online focus groups, teleconference tools offer this possibility.
- Additional resources for people who need support to participate:
- Description of images on presentation
- Assistants for people who need support to participate (additional financial resources may be required for fees)
- Travel vouchers if geographical/economic barriers are foreseen and no possibility for online focus group is available
- If the focus group is conducted face-to-face:
- Pens for each participant, wallpaper or whiteboard, sticky notes
- Catering may be needed, depending on the duration of the session (additional financial resources may be required)

Procedure

The technique involves conversations structured around 2-3 questions on the specific topic to arrive to a decision point, working best when participants are provided with specific information. This can be provided with some days in advance but should be present during the session in case the participants could not read the information prior to the activity, or any questions arise.

Before organising a focus group, the facilitator should first define the stakes and goals of the evaluation and determine the questions to which the focus group will provide answers. The input from the focus group can be recorded on a laptop and viewed on a screen by everyone, if it is carried out online; an alternative is to use a platform to post the contributions, such as Miro board (<https://miro.com>). Some examples have been prepared in the section [Templates for Miro boards](#) of this document.

- Face-to-face: If the focus groups are performed face-to-face, other possibility is to use post its on a paper wall. This allows the facilitator to take the participants through a visual summary of the content they have generated together before proceeding to another stage of the conversation with the focus group; and it allows the participants to review what they have said and make any corrections or changes to what is being recorded to ensure it reflects their input accurately. The recording (with previous consent of participants) facilitates the transcription of the focus groups and analysis of data. This process is highly transparent and allows quick preparation of a report for participants and decision makers.
- In the absence of recording, it can be interesting to organise a briefing session, in order to validate the content of the focus group's transcription.
- The analysis of the focus groups results is based on the following:
 - Identification of topics: relying on the transcription, assign tags to the different sections of the text corresponding to the topics of the research and look for patterns. These will depend on the objectives of the research.
 - Look for relations between the topics detected. These are the patterns of the conversation. Looking for patterns will imply refining the codes and the tags assigned in the previous stage.
 - Codification and categorization of responses: organize systematically the responses based on the topics and patterns identified. This process allows the aggregation and comparison of the responses, easing the obtention of conclusions. Develop a “book of topics” with the codes, definitions and examples of each code. Apply the codes to the different parts of the conversation and group similar codes to set up categories

- Extraction of insights: Based on the codes, extract the main results in a coherent narrative. Use direct citations to illustrate key points and identify general trends to provide a comprehensive understanding of the participants' point of views-
- Relate the insights with the objectives of the research, extracting recommendations linked to the different topics.

Figure 11. Example of Miro board for 3 questions in focus group

9.3. World Café

10. This participatory approach can be used to explore a range of themes or questions.
11. It involves small group conversations around tables, with participants switching tables and sharing insights as they move around. The approach allows a diverse range of stakeholders to engage in conversations and share perspectives, promoting collaboration and knowledge sharing, identifying opportunities, etc.
12. The process starts with a facilitator that sets the context for the conversation and invites participants to converse in their host table, and to move around to other tables to share opinions with other participants. After a defined time moving around the tables, participants come back to their host table and share experiences and new insights. The more conversations the participant share, the broader their perspective become, allowing them to understand other positions.

Figure 12. World cafe concept. Source: <https://urbact.eu>

Duration

Minimum 2 hours. Can be extended to a period of sessions depending on the complexity of the topic or decisions to be taken.

Public

Minimum 12 attendees. No maximum

Resources

- A place with natural light, comfortable. Special attention must be paid to sound, avoiding places with high reverberation, since it will make difficult to keep conversation. Usually theatre halls, sport halls and similar facilities have adequate rooms). Cushions, textiles and plants can be used to enhance comfort (attention to allergies).
- Tables and chairs: the World Café works best with four or five people per table. If the group is larger, dialogue breaks down, as some people tend to take over the conversation while others remain silent. On the other hand, 3 people do not bring enough diversity of perspective. Tables should not be too big (90-100 cm diameter is suitable), avoiding the need to raise the voices, and facilitating intimate connection.

- Paper to cover each table and pens/markers for each participant to write with. Participants will note and draw their ideas and thoughts on the table on the different questions posed. The host in each table will remind the others to note their ideas and thoughts and always repeats to the new group what before was discussed at this particular table.

Procedure:

1. Setting the context: Brochures and documentation can be sent some days in advance, to prepare participants with good information on the activity. However, it is foreseeable that participants have not enough time to read the documentation or ignore it due to previous expectations or experiences. Thus, the World Café session must start with a context of the session:
 - Backgrounds (bioeconomy concepts, challenges, opportunities, specific topic of a sector, etc).
 - Why participants have been invited.
 - What contribution is expected from them.
2. Creation of a safe and hospitable space: crowded spaces may be uncomfortable for some people for many reasons. It is the role of the facilitators to create an adequate environment. A basic step is explaining the principles that will be used through the session (respect, not interrupting, active listening etc), known as “Table Etiquette”. Depending on resources, further actions can be implemented:
 - Tables should not be too big, to allow hosts in each of them to communicate in an intimate matter, with no need to raise the voice
 - Setting up food and drinks in each table to share.
 - Ideally, a table host should be in each table to greet people and helping them feel welcome, as well as acting as moderator to ensure participation. The table host does not move around tables and acts as a member of the conversation.
 - The freedom to move from one table to another alleviates hierarchies and power imbalances, since people feel free to express opinions and the person who leads conversation in a table becomes a participant in other.
3. Setting the questions: The questions asked in a World Café play a critical role in the success of the project and should encourage innovation and the acquisition of knowledge not already obtained by the promoters.
 - Questions should be open to foster conversation (for instance, how, what, why, when, where)
 - It is important to determine the scope of the question (an individual, team, company, community, region, etc)

- Questions shall not imply assumptions: If we ask about “how beneficial is bioeconomy for you” we are assuming that a benefit exists and may create discomfort or suspicion among participants; on the other hand, asking about “how does this project/regulation impact your activity” the impact may be positive or negative.
- Instead of trying to cover a lot of issues with many questions, it is recommendable to focus on key aspects and have questions that can be used as lever, to further explore a topic.

12.1. Impact Mapping

This technique is used to understand the wider impacts of a project or activity and of the materiality of these impacts. It can be used to assess the achievement of Sustainable Development Goal. Impact mapping draws on theory-based evaluation methods (Theory of Change, ToC) to sketch plausible causal pathways from activities to the results (tailored for different groups of stakeholders), to sustainability impact, allowing to screen and prioritise issues. It is a visualisation of scope for a certain project or activity, and the underlying assumptions, created collaboratively.

Duration:

About 3-4 hours. Can be extended to a period of sessions depending on the complexity of the topic or break into smaller sessions.

Public:

1 to 10 people. Can be performed with big groups but may take a longer time for each step.

Resources

- Laptop, data projector, screen.
- Hard copies and PowerPoint reference material on the topic
- For online Impact mapping workshop:
 - Online platform to post contributions: Miro boards (<https://miro.com>), with a grid previously prepared by the facilitator).
- For offline/ Impact mapping workshop:
 - A meeting room to seat 10 to 20 people comfortably at tables in a u-shape setting

- a large whiteboard
- whiteboard markers
- sticky notes
- markers for sticky notes

Procedure

As a preliminary work, the facilitator team should generate the grid/template on which the participants will work, and elaborate the information required to be delivered on previous days and kept available during the workshop session.

The workshop in the impact mapping technique is divided in 4 stages, to produce a final graph. All participants can draw in the map, for which additional training/assistance may be required when using a digital platform. Letting the facilitator be the only person updating the online map, they will become the single point of failure.

1. Definition of the goal. It represents the centre of the impact map, answering the most important question: why are we doing this?
2. Actors/stakeholders: Represents the first branch of the tree, responding to the question “who” is answered, embodying the actors who can influence the outcome are listed. To this aim, the following questions are asked.
 - Who can produce the required effect?
 - Who can obstruct it?
 - Who will benefit of our activity?
 - Who will be impacted by it?
3. Impacts: is the second branch of the impact map, responding to the question “how”. It is the impact that we want to achieve in each of the actors presented in the previous branch. The following questions are asked, and usually quantified (i.e. increase of 10% of demand of wood products, decreased 5% taxes in bioplastic packaging):
 - How should our actors’ behaviour change?
 - How can they help us achieve our goal?
 - How can they prevent to achieve the goal?
4. Deliverables. Once we have the previous questions answered, the deliverables inform about the scope of the impact, answering to the question: “what can be done to achieve the impact? The answers are typically products or features, such as a software, an application, an eco-brand to standardise a product, etc

Figure 13. Impact map template. Source: <https://tomd.xyz>

12.2. Scenario planning

Scenario planning is a well-suited approach for strategical thinking coping with uncertainty (required due to unpredictability and variability of future) and complex systems (encompassing a wide number of interdependent factors or dimensions), while improving strategic thinking, creativity, and learning.

The method called European Awareness Scenario Workshops (EASW) rises the challenge of facing the environmental problems of our living areas (towns - cities or villages) by their own inhabitants, including all stakeholders (civil society, decision makers, research and education actors, and private sector such as industry or commerce) (Gnaiger and Schroffenegger, 2003).

Duration:

The original method comprises 2 days. It can be shortened combining stages, to avoid barriers in participation.

Public:

24 to 36 participants with balanced representation of all sectors. (civil society, decision makers, research and education actors, and private sector such as industry or commerce).

Resources

- Local organiser or facilitator. The facilitator should be well informed of the evaluation's topics and goals, be familiar with all the techniques relating to group interaction and speak the language of the participants.
- Venue: A room with tables and chairs that can be shaped in U.
- Laptop, data projector, screen.
- Video-camera with audio-recorder: to register the progress of the scenario planning and to analyse the results (informed consent for recording will be required)
- Hard copies and PowerPoint reference material on the topic
- Additional resources for people who need support to participate:
- Description of images on presentation
- Travel vouchers if geographical/economic barriers are foreseen and no possibility for online implementation is available.
- Financial resources for catering, accommodation, etc.

Procedure

Figure 14. Scenarios classification

During the scenario planning workshop, participants are divided in 4 groups where they discuss current and future problems, seek solutions and suggest changes that are crucial for the improvement of their region, and its sustainable development.

The method comprises the following phases:

DAY 1.

1. Introduction and incentive. Short presentation of the meaning of the different scenarios, from the best case (positive) to be worst case (negative). This can be supported by presentations and documents as inspiration material, showcasing best practices and initiatives carried out in the field of bioeconomy (in the sectors dominant in each region, or emerging/potential sectors according to Smart and Sustainable Strategies). Participants take part in the elaboration of the scenarios, through post its and debates. The scenarios are sorted by the role of technology and the need of collective and individual actions (Figure 14).
 - Best case scenario: The bioeconomy model region we want for 2030. Describing the potentialities and situations that would satisfy the participants.
 - Worst case scenario: The bioeconomy model region we don't want for 2030. Challenges and fears (i.e. losing jobs, high prices of food make it not affordable etc)
2. Stating ideas in role groups. Participants divided in four role groups, according to their expertise i.e. civil society, professionals and industry representatives, decision makers of civil servants, and researchers/experts, express their ideas with regard to the sustainable region of 2030 based on the previous scenarios and their previous experience. After two-by-two persons discussions (double interviewing) to sort the different alternatives, the main objectives for a sustainable future are selected and registered on a poster. As a result, 4 different posters are obtained.
3. General assembly. Each group present their poster, and a discussion of the role groups' ideas follows. Results will be taken as the starting point for the next day's work.

DAY 2. "What should be done?"

1. Group discussion: Participants will be divided into four different theme groups related to what "should be done „about implementing their views” in different areas (these can be agriculture, biotechnology, forest management, waste management, energy, etc). The technique of writing cards or sticky notes to propose actions is used, and each participant records their ideas for actions. The group facilitator presents all the ideas to in the group and the feasibility of each idea is discussed. The actions selected by the group are presented in a poster that will be presented to the general assembly.
2. Selection and assessment of ideas. The ideas proposed in the groups are discussed together with the feasibility, summarized in the posters. First, general

votes prioritise the proposals. Participants are requested to cast a given number of votes (5 or 6). They can vote any proposed actions, which are presented, except those proposed by their own groups.

3. Final steps. "Who and How". Proposals are evaluated following the scenario approach. The solutions are defined according to the technologies required and the responsibilities (whether they should be done individually or collectively). The ideas and conclusions of the workshop are disseminated among relevant stakeholders.

EVALUATION:

After the activity, organisers (RC leaders) will evaluate the Scenario planning based on the following dimensions. This can be supported by feedback of the participants using surveys and questionnaires:

- a. Duration:
 - Was it adequate to address all the topics during the debate?
 - Was any of the stages shortened due to time constraints?
 - Was it too long, producing demotivation?
- b. Procedures:
 - Did the procedure promote a dialogue between all interested parties and local groups?
 - Did conflicts arise between parties and local groups?
 - How did the facilitator manage the conflicts?
 - Were the scenarios presented significant to the local context?
 - Were the tools (documentations, slideshows) adequate and present updated information?
 - Did these tools take into account diversity of perspectives and case studies, or did they rather present a "mainstream" vision?
 - Was the procedure for voting the actions proposed transparent and allowed all the actions to be presented and voted?
- c. Number and quality of the actors participating:
 - Was the number of participants enough to represent different stakeholders?
 - Was any relevant group not present (i.e. youth, workers)

This evaluation will allow to detect strengths and limitations of the Activity and the conclusions reached, and to seek for further improvements.

12.3. Role playing

Role playing has been used to study social issues (i.e. race, ethnicity, social inequality, gender, social exclusion). The technique is a game-like activity based on the interpretation/performance of one or more characters in a story. It can also be used as a narration (storytelling). The participants may assume to represent themselves or another person in a different situation, condition, etc., in a safe environment, where they can act, experiment, learn and teach without running the risk of suffering irreversible consequences, approximating “aspects of life”, events or experiences in “controlled conditions”. There are different variants (Tsergas, 2021) depending on the number of participants; the performance face-to-face or online (i.e. through videogames); or the static/dynamic structure (participants keeping the same role during the game or changing roles to explore different perspectives).

Duration

Minimum 1 hour. Can be extended depending on the complexity of situation (number of roles or stakeholders involved), the number of participants (in big groups, too short role playing may impede some stakeholders to actively participate); the dynamic selected for role playing (if changing roles is planned, the technique will take longer to repeat the situation with different actors in each role).

Public

Role playing can be used in small groups in a closed place, and bigger groups in natural environment. Smaller groups facilitate participation and avoid people to adopt passive roles.

Resources

- A facilitator skilled in role playing.
- A script for role playing defines the different roles that will be used during the activity, with the basic characteristics (positions, behaviours, etc), and the situation that will be played.
- Documentation on the topic and the different roles (i.e. circumstances of women, farmers, policy makers, fishers or any other actor in the socio-ecosystem).
- A place for role playing. It can be a closed or open space but should provide space for participants to move around. Usually theatre halls, sport halls and similar facilities have adequate rooms).

- Optionally, we can provide elements such as clothes, textiles, objects that help to build the dramatic scene.

Procedure

Role playing procedure can be divided into 3 stages:

1. Preparing for the roleplay: Refers to psychological and sometimes, also physical preparation of both the participants and the facilitator. First, an issue or a problem is chosen to explore its possible solutions. It is also important that participants have a good knowledge of the topic, for which documentation has to be prepared and distributed in advance and kept on hand during the workshop/activity. This can be performed by participants themselves (which makes the activity more collaborative) or by the facilitator. Next, a script is formed, and the roles are assigned to the participants. *Example of script: In region X, the pollution of a small coastal lagoon has happened, due to eutrophication. Agriculture is a highly important activity in the region that represents a significant part of the GDP, but other activities have been impacted: tourism has decreased, mainly in summer, due to the jellyfish and algal blooms; fishermen have seen a drastic reduction of captures due to anoxic conditions that caused fish death; many jobs have been lost as a consequence; public administrators had fostered uncontrolled urbanisation to host all the tourism (hotels, residential tourism) which has also increased water demand. Roles to be played: farmers, inhabitants, tourism business, fishermen, fish/birds (representing nature). Each role group should first explain their needs and expectations, and then look for a collective solution-*
2. Role-playing: This is the main phase, when the role-playing is being carried out, and the set is arranged accordingly to the script written in the previous stage. The facilitator coordinates the game and can interrupt it, if needed, to discuss issues, clarify attitudes or behaviours. With the permission of participants, the role playing can be recorded for further analysis after the activity, using a video-camera.
3. After the roleplay: Discussion and assessment. Upon completion of the roleplay, there is a discussion for participants to gain insight into the learning experience. During this phase, participants get gradually out of the roles they had assumed while role-playing and are encouraged to express their feelings and their thoughts during the group discussion.
4. Analysis and evaluation: During this stage, other complementary activities can be carried out to process the learnings and summarize the impacts: a poster, a paint or collage, etc. These learnings are often related to generating alternatives and evaluating options to a wicked problem and the development of required skills such as effective communication, empathy, collaboration, persuasion and conflict handling. The following questions can be answered by the participants in the role play and summarized in a report, aided by the video recording and transcription:

- How did you feel in the role you played? Comfortable, uncomfortable, empowered, disempowered, impatient?
- If the role play aimed at solving a complex problem:
 - How many solutions or alternatives were proposed?
 - How do you feel about the solution reached?
 - How did each agent contribute to the solution? Did you feel listened or taken into account?
 - Did you find easier to find a common solution with some agents or others? Which ones? Why?
 - Was it more difficult to find a solution with any of the agents? Which ones? Why?

